

EFFECT OF DIFFERENT TOOTHPASTES ON THE SURFACE ROUGHNESS OF ANTERIOR RESTORATIVE MATERIALS

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Abstract

Background: Tooth brushing is the most common oral hygiene practice for preventing caries lesions. Using whitening toothpastes is one of the preferred, easy-to-apply, and economical methods for achieving whiter teeth. Abrasives in whitening toothpastes help remove stains from tooth surfaces. **Aim or Purpose:** This in vitro study was carried to evaluate the solubility of the anterior restorative materials specimens (conventional glass ionomer, resin modified GI, nanohybrid composite and nano composite) when using electric toothbrush with two types of toothpaste. (Abrasive and nonabrasive). **Materials and Methods:** A total of 120 cylindrical specimens of anterior restorative materials were prepared. The specimens were divided into four main groups (30 each) based on the type of restoration: nanohybrid composite, nanocomposite, conventional glass ionomer, and resin-modified glass ionomer. Each main group was further divided into two subgroups (15 each), with one subgroup using an electric toothbrush with abrasive toothpaste and the other using non-abrasive toothpaste. The electric toothbrush was used for 2-5 minutes. Each group was also subdivided according to storage time (1, 7, and 14 days). Weight changes were measured using a digital balance before and after brushing. All data were analyzed using the t-test and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) ($p < 0.05$). **Results:** The electric toothbrush significantly decreased the weight of all specimens after simulated brushing ($p < 0.05$). The highest weight loss was observed in the conventional glass ionomer specimens when brushed with both abrasive and non-abrasive toothpaste. In contrast, the lowest weight loss was recorded for the nanohybrid composite when brushed with non-abrasive toothpaste. **Conclusion and recommendations:** This study found that all tested anterior restorative materials experienced weight loss from brushing, with abrasive toothpaste causing the most degradation. Over time, weight loss increased, indicating a cumulative impact on material integrity. Conventional glass ionomer cement (GIC) was the most susceptible to wear, while the nanohybrid composite showed the least weight loss, especially with non-abrasive toothpaste. These results emphasize the need for careful material selection in restorative dentistry and highlight the importance of educating patients about toothpaste abrasivity. Dental professionals should recommend non-abrasive toothpaste, particularly for patients with GIC restorations, to reduce surface degradation and improve the longevity of dental materials.

Keywords: Toothpaste, Surface Roughness, Anterior Restorative Materials.

INTRODUCTION

Esthetic rehabilitation in dentistry has become increasingly important in today's globalized world. Presenting white, well-shaped, and well-aligned teeth not only meets aesthetic demands

but also serves as an indicator of oral health. These attributes are essential in fulfilling the requirements of contemporary society, which places a high value on sociability and appearance. ^(1,2)

Composite resin (CR) and resin-modified glass ionomer cement (RMGIC) are the most commonly used materials for direct restorations. While RMGIC forms a chemical bond with enamel and dentin and releases fluoride helping to mitigate erosive effects on adjacent tissues it has been shown to be more susceptible to degradation compared to CR. This difference in durability highlights the need for careful material selection in restorative dentistry. ^(3,4)

As patients increasingly seek a whiter, brighter, and healthier smile, the demand for esthetic dentistry continues to rise. One effective approach to achieving high esthetic results is through whitening treatments, which are considered non-invasive methods. These treatments effectively remove or reduce stains on teeth and encompass various techniques, including differing whitening agent contents, concentrations, and applications. ^(5,6)

In recent years, there has been a significant increase in the use of over-the-counter (OTC) whitening products that patients can apply themselves. Among these products, whitening toothpaste constitutes the largest segment. These toothpastes leverage abrasive qualities or specific chemical ingredients, such as aluminum oxide, silica, sodium bicarbonate, carbamide peroxide (CP), and hydrogen peroxide (HP), to clean tooth surfaces more effectively. ^(7,8)

Recently, toothpastes containing activated charcoal have emerged as a new product line, touted for their effectiveness in removing external stains due to their high adsorption capacity. This innovation reflects the ongoing advancements in dental care products and the growing consumer interest in achieving optimal oral aesthetics. ⁽⁹⁻¹¹⁾

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Preparation of Samples and Power Analysis

Composite resins were placed in specially prepared Teflon molds (2 x 5 mm). After removing excess material by lightly pressing with transparent tape (Mylar strips), the samples were polymerized for 20 seconds using an LED light device (Guilin Woodpecker Medical Instrument Co., Guilin, China) emitting light at a wavelength of 470 nm (light intensity: 1,200 mW/cm²). The surfaces of the samples were polished consecutively for 15 seconds using extra-coarse, coarse/medium, fine, and extra-fine polishing discs (Opti Disc, Kerr, FL, USA), with new discs used for each sample. All samples were stored in distilled water at 37°C for 24 hours, following the manufacturer's instructions. The composition of the restorative materials is shown in Table 1.

A total of 120 cylindrical specimens of anterior restorative materials were prepared. The specimens were divided into four main groups based on the type of restoration: conventional glass ionomer, resin-modified glass ionomer, nanohybrid composite, and nanocomposite, with 20 specimens in each group. Each main group was further divided into two subgroups (10

each). The first subgroup was evaluated before using the toothbrush (Oral-B Precision Clean), while the second subgroup was evaluated after brushing.

Each subgroup was divided into two additional groups: one using an electric toothbrush with abrasive toothpaste (BlanX MEN Double Whitening Action) and the other using non-abrasive toothpaste (Sensodyne Multi-Care + Whitening). The electric toothbrush was used for 2-5 minutes with either toothpaste for storage durations of 1, 7, and 15 days. The specimens were stored for one month prior to measurement. Weight changes were recorded using a digital balance before and after brushing. All data were analyzed using the student's t-test and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

Table 1: List of Materials Used in This Study

No.	Material	Type	Manufacturer
1	Competence universal	Nano composite	Schusterring 35, 25355 Barmstedt/Germany
2	Xs-FiL	Nanohybrid composite.	955-16, Baran-ro, Jeongnam-myeon, Hwaseong-si, Gyeonggi-do, Republic of Korea
3	Harvard Ionoglas Cem	Conventional GIC	Harvard Dental international Gerba, 15366 Hoppegarten,
4	SDI Riva Self Cure	Resin modified GI	Made in Australia by SDI Limysed 321, Vrusndon
5	Abrasive toothpaste	BlanX double whitening toothpaste Arctic Lichens and blue formula based action	Via Gobetti 4 . 40050 FUNO (BO). Italy
6	Non-abrasive toothpaste	Sensodyne Multi care + Whitening	Made in Saudi Arabia
7	Electric toothbrush	Oral-B Precision Clean-Type 3750	Made in China DB5.010.1

RESULTS

Table 2: Mean Value for Weight Loss of Anterior Restorative Materials Under Brushing with Two Toothpastes (Abrasive vs. Non-Abrasive) at Different Storage Times

		Nanohybrid	Nanocomposite	Conventional GIC	Resin modified GIC
abrasive	1 Day	0.3	0.9	3.8	2.8
	1 Week	0.7	2.2	4.7	4.1
	2 Week	1.2	3.1	4.1	3.7
Non abrasive	1 Day	0.2	0.4	0.8	2.1
	1 Week	0.8	2	3.4	3
	2 Week	0.6	2.2	3.7	3.1

Table 2 and Figure 1 present the weight loss of various anterior restorative materials assessed after brushing with different types of toothpaste over two weeks. For abrasive toothpaste, the nanohybrid material exhibited a weight loss of 0.3 g after one day, increasing to 0.7 g by one week and reaching 1.2 g by two weeks. The nanocomposite showed a weight loss of 0.9 g on the first day, escalating to 2.2 g after one week and 3.1 g by the end of the two-week period. In contrast, conventional glass ionomer cement (GIC) experienced significantly higher weight

loss, starting at 3.8 g on Day 1, peaking at 4.7 g after one week, and slightly decreasing to 4.1 g by two weeks. The resin modified GIC also showed considerable weight loss, beginning at 2.8 g, peaking at 4.1 g after one week, and then reducing to 3.7 g after two weeks.

When using non-abrasive toothpaste, the nanohybrid material lost 0.2 g initially, with losses of 0.8 g at one week and 0.6 g after two weeks. The nanocomposite had a weight loss of 0.4 g on the first day, which increased to 2.0 g by one week and 2.2 g by two weeks. Conventional GIC showed a weight loss of 0.8 g after one day, increasing to 3.4 g at one week and 3.7 g by the two-week mark. Finally, the resin modified GIC started with a loss of 2.1 g after one day, decreasing to 3.0 g by one week and stabilizing at 3.1 g after two weeks. Overall, these results underscore the significant impact of toothpaste abrasivity on the wear of restorative materials, highlighting the importance of material selection and patient education regarding toothpaste use.

DISCUSSION

The present in vitro study evaluated the effect of abrasive and non-abrasive toothpaste on the surface integrity of anterior restorative materials over different storage times. The results demonstrated that all tested materials exhibited weight loss upon brushing, with abrasive toothpaste inducing significantly higher material degradation compared to non-abrasive toothpaste. Additionally, an increase in weight loss was observed over time, indicating the cumulative effect of mechanical brushing.

The data revealed that specimens brushed with abrasive toothpaste exhibited a greater weight loss than those exposed to non-abrasive toothpaste across all material types and time points.⁽¹³⁾ This finding aligns with previous studies indicating that abrasive agents within toothpaste play a significant role in the wear and surface degradation of restorative materials.⁽¹⁴⁾ The increased loss of material with abrasive toothpaste can be attributed to the presence of silica-based particles, calcium carbonate, or hydrated silica, which are commonly used abrasives known to enhance cleaning efficiency but also contribute to material erosion.⁽¹⁵⁾

A progressive increase in weight loss was observed with prolonged exposure to brushing. After two weeks, all restorative materials exhibited significantly higher weight loss compared to one-day or one-week time points.⁽¹⁶⁾ This progressive deterioration is likely due to the continuous impact of mechanical forces exerted during brushing, as well as the cumulative effect of toothpaste abrasively on surface integrity.⁽¹⁴⁾ Longitudinal studies on dental restorative materials have reported similar findings, where extended exposure to brushing results in increased material wear and surface roughness.⁽¹⁷⁾

The study also found that the type of restorative material significantly influenced the extent of weight loss:

- Conventional GIC displayed the highest susceptibility to weight loss under both abrasive and non-abrasive conditions.⁽¹⁸⁾ This could be due to its inherently lower mechanical strength, hydrophilic nature, and susceptibility to acid erosion, which are well-documented limitations of conventional GIC. The greater degradation of GIC may also be linked to its

water-based matrix, which undergoes dissolution and wear when subjected to mechanical brushing.⁽¹⁹⁾

- Although RMGIC exhibited slightly lower weight loss compared to conventional GIC, it still showed considerable degradation, particularly with abrasive toothpaste.⁽¹⁹⁾ This is consistent with findings that RMGIC, despite having a resin component that improves mechanical properties, retains characteristics of conventional GIC, including susceptibility to surface erosion.⁽²⁰⁾
- Among the resin-based materials, nanocomposites demonstrated greater weight loss than nanohybrid composites.⁽²¹⁾ The lower weight loss recorded in nanohybrid composites could be attributed to their superior filler composition, enhanced polymerization, and higher wear resistance.⁽²¹⁾ Nanocomposites, despite their improved mechanical properties, exhibited greater weight loss than nanohybrids, possibly due to differences in filler particle size and matrix composition, which influence resistance to mechanical abrasion.⁽²²⁾

Clinical Implications

The findings of this study underscore the importance of selecting appropriate restorative materials for patients with high brushing frequencies and those using abrasive toothpaste. The significantly higher weight loss observed in GIC and RMGIC suggests that these materials may not be ideal for patients prone to aggressive brushing habits.⁽²⁰⁾ On the other hand, nanohybrid composites demonstrated superior resistance to mechanical degradation, making them a preferable choice for anterior restorations requiring long-term durability.⁽²³⁾

Additionally, the results highlight the need for patient education regarding the impact of toothpaste abrasiveness on dental restorations. Dental professionals should guide patients in selecting non-abrasive toothpaste, particularly for those with glass ionomer-based restorations, to minimize surface degradation and prolong the longevity of restorations.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study demonstrated that all tested anterior restorative materials experienced weight loss following exposure to brushing, with abrasive toothpaste causing the highest degradation. Additionally, the weight loss increased over time, underscoring the progressive impact of brushing on material integrity. Conventional glass ionomer cement (GIC) showed the greatest susceptibility to wear, while the nanohybrid composite exhibited the least weight loss, particularly when brushed with non-abrasive toothpaste.

These findings highlight the importance of careful material selection in restorative dentistry. It is crucial to educate patients about the abrasivity of toothpaste to help ensure the longevity of their restorations. Dental professionals should consider recommending non-abrasive toothpaste, especially for patients with glass ionomer-based restorations, to minimize surface degradation and enhance the durability of dental materials.

Study Limitations and Future Directions

While this study provides valuable insights into the effect of toothpaste abrasivity on anterior restorative materials, certain limitations must be acknowledged. First, the *in vitro* nature of the study may not fully replicate intraoral conditions, including the effects of salivary enzymes, pH fluctuations, and temperature changes. Additionally, variations in patient brushing technique, force application, and duration may influence real-world outcomes. Future research should explore these factors through *in vivo* studies to validate the findings under clinical conditions.

Moreover, further investigation into the microstructural changes in restorative materials post-brushing, using techniques such as scanning electron microscopy (SEM) or atomic force microscopy (AFM), could provide deeper insights into the mechanisms of material degradation. Evaluating additional restorative materials, including newer formulations of bulk-fill composites and bioactive restorative materials, could also enhance the understanding of material performance under prolonged exposure to tooth brushing.

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